

Catastrophic marine mass mortalities, shellfish toxicity and human respiratory problems from a *Karenia cristata* dinoflagellate bloom in South Australia, 2025–2026

Fig. 1. Satellite chlorophyll image from March 2024 showing widespread offshore diatom blooms in response to a massive upwelling event during the year preceding the 2025 *Karenia* bloom, which occurred mainly within Spencer Gulf and Gulf St Vincent, South Australia. <https://oceancurrent.aodn.org.au>.

In early March 2025, surfers off the Fleurieu Peninsula, near Adelaide (South Australia), began suffering respiratory irritation, which they linked to a yellow-green algal bloom (Fig. 1), accompanied by a thick sea foam and dead marine life washing up onshore (Fig. 2). The bloom subsequently expanded to Yorke Peninsula, Kangaroo Island, Gulf St Vincent, and parts of the Spencer Gulf. As of May 2026, 15 months later, *Karenia* species are still present at abundances of $\sim 10^4$ cells L⁻¹ in some coastal areas of South Australia, although both abundances and distribution have markedly declined from their peak in mid-to-late 2025. Surfers, beachgoers and coastal residents reported illnesses ranging from skin and eye irritation to respiratory symptoms such as coughing and shortness of breath. Public health advisories recommended avoiding affected waters and bloom-generated foams and seeking medical attention if symptoms develop. Testing of commercially harvested oysters, mussels, cockles and scallops detected brevetoxins in shellfish, resulting in the closure of some South Australian oyster harvesting areas for approximately eight months during 2025.

Satellite images of the chlorophyll-a anomalies over the past 20 years, covering the period from May to September 2025 [5] showed that the anomalously high chlorophyll region covered an

estimated 20,000 km². Mass mortalities affected at least 770 marine fish, mammals, birds and invertebrates, also disrupting commercial fisheries (calamari), aquaculture (abalone) and tourism industries (<https://www.inaturalist.org/projects/sa-marine-mortality-events-2025-2026>). Previously known marine HAB-forming taxa in the region [1] included species causing water discolorations (*Noctiluca*), those responsible for fish kills (*Heterosigma akashiwo*, *Chattonella marina*, *Karenia mikimotoi*), producing seafood toxins (*Alexandrium minutum*, *A. pacificum*). However, such a prolonged marine mass mortality event affecting fish, mammals, birds and invertebrates, combined with associated human health impacts, had never previously been documented in Australia.

Fig. 2. Seafoam and dead fish on Adelaide beaches, May–October 2025. Photos: Samantha Sea; Shauna Murray.

Water testing in March 2025 revealed the co-occurrence of several *Karenia* species, including *Karenia mikimotoi* [2]. Blooms of this species had previously been recorded in the region in March 1995 and February–March 2014 [3–4], during which massive fish-kill events occurred. In May 2025, brevetoxins were confirmed for the first time in Australian waters, suggesting the presence of a brevetoxin-producing *Karenia* species. A massive six-month effort by 24 scientists [5] from 10 organisations in Australia, New Zealand, and the U.K., led by Professor Shauna Murray, involved culturing, light and scanning electron microscopy, molecular techniques, and toxin chemistry analyses (partly funded by the Fisheries Research and Development Corporation, FRDC). This work ultimately identified and confirmed *K. cristata* as the toxin-producing species, with a brevetoxin profile (BTX-2, BTX-3, BTX-B5), that differs from the well-studied *K. brevis*, as it does not produce BTX-1 (Type A) analogues.

The dinoflagellate *K. cristata* (Fig. 3) had previously only been reported from two cold-water locations: False Bay and Walker Bay, South Africa [6], in the mid-1990s, and a remote island off the coast of Newfoundland (French Territory) [7]. The pale yellow-green cells (21–32 μ m long, 16–29 μ m wide) were fragile, fast swimming, dorso-ventrally compressed (9–14 μ m deep), and consisted of a short hemispherical epicone with a minute apical crest (cr;

from which the species name *cristata* is derived), and a longer hypocone with the right lobe slightly longer than the left. Scanning electron microscopy revealed that the crest was formed by a slight elevation of the right side of the apical groove. On the dorsal side, the apical groove extended to one-third of the epicone length. Living cells exhibited a large centrally located nucleus (N), unlike *K. mikimotoi*, in which the nucleus is positioned on the left side of the hypocone. Upon Lugol's iodine preservation, cells often displayed a more pointed epicone and a more pronounced apical crest, with the nucleus positioned lower in the hypocone. The sulcal intrusion (si) was either wide-open or terminated in a finger-like projection. This species closely resembles the Chinese *Karenia hui* (also possessing an apical crest), as well as *Karenia selliformis* (but with two equal hypoconal lobes). Both latter species differ in possessing a large elongate hypoconal nucleus. A qPCR assay for *K. hui* and *K. selliformis* showed no cross-reactivity with *K. cristata* (from cultures or environmental samples), while *K. brevis* was never detected in the South Australian bloom [5].

The environmental drivers behind this unprecedented HAB are currently subject of intense investigation. A sustained massive upwelling event started in the summer of 2023/2024 (Fig. 1). Other notable oceanographic events over the period were a marine heat wave in early 2025, characterised by water temperatures approximately 2 degrees warmer than normal in the months preceding the HAB, and nutrient enrichment several years earlier associated with flooding of the Murray/Darling river system. The Great Southern Australian Upwelling System [9] commonly triggers diatom blooms that support high productivity of sardine and tuna populations, as well as a high biodiversity of seals, whales, dolphins, sharks, and seabirds. In the past, upwelling relaxation in this region has only rarely led to inshore *Karenia mikimotoi* dinoflagellate blooms (e.g. 2014 in Coffin Bay). The multifactorial conditions that facilitated *Karenia cristata* to newly generate such long-lasting, persistent ecosystem disruptive HAB event inside the Spencer Gulf and Gulf of St Vincent remain unresolved.

Fig. 3. *Karenia cristata* from South Australia. Light micrographs of (A) living and (B) Lugol-preserved cells, showing the apical crest (cr) and nucleus position (N). Scanning electron micrographs of (C) a whole cell in ventral view, showing the right hypoconal lobe longer than the left lobe; (D) high-magnification detail of the ventral view of the sulcal intrusion (si), with the right edge (arrow) of the straight apical groove (ag) elevated; and (E) dorsal view of the apical groove extending one-third of the length of the epitheca. Images: (A) S. Murray; (B) C. Wilkinson; (C–E) G. Hallegraeff.

This recent South Australian HAB has highlighted a critical need to strengthen preparedness frameworks at Australian state and national levels. Long-term HAB management is currently not specifically addressed in existing environmental, biosecurity, human health or climate-change policies in Australia [10]. A professional network for researchers and stakeholders in marine HAB science was established in 2025 with the formation of ANZHAB-NET (11), and funding for HAB monitoring, mitigation, restoration, and research has begun to be made available.

The implications of this event for the global HAB community are profound. We now recognize a second high-brevetoxin producing *Karenia* species that poses a new threat to marine ecosystems and human health. This species distribution and ecology needs to be urgently investigated, not just in Australia, but any waters with comparable conditions.

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